

Kinetics of Reactions of Alcohols with HBr Solvent and Temperature Influences

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Kinetics of reactions of monohydric alcohols with HBr in non-aqueous systems is reported. The effects of temperature and solvent on reactions of diols with HBr is also investigated. The results are rationalised on the basis of previously postulated mechanism involving neighbouring group participation.

In our previous communications^{1,2,3,4} we reported the kinetics of reactions of glycols with hydrogen halides in various non-aqueous systems. The present communication deals with the structural and solvent influences for reactions in the monohydric alcohols and effect of temperature and solvent for reactions with diols.

EXPERIMENTAL

The solvents used, glacial acetic acid, benzene, monochloro acetic acid, propionic acid, carbon tetrachloride and acetonitrile, were purified by the usual procedure and distilled. The substrates used were of guaranteed quality or distilled before use.

The physical constants of the purified substances were as follows :

Acetic acid b.p. 118°; n_D^{20} 1.3683, benzene b.p. 80°; n_D^{20} 1.5011, monochloro acetic acid b.p. 189°; n_D^{65} 1.4297, propionic acid b.p. 141°; n_D^{20} 1.3874, carbon tetrachloride b.p. 77°; n_D^{15} 1.4630, acetonitrile b.p. 81.5°; n_D^{20} 1.3442, methanol b.p. 65°; n_D^{20} 1.3288, ethanol b.p. 78°; n_D^{20} 1.361; *n*-propanol b.p. 97°; n_D^{20} 1.3854, *n*-butanol b.p. 118°; n_D^{20} 1.3991, ethylene glycol b.p. 197°; n_D^{20} 1.429, propylene glycol b.p. 189°; n_D^{20} 1.4293, 1 : 3 butane diol b.p. 207°; n_D^{20} 1.4418.

Hydrobromic acid used is a freshly distilled azeotropic mixture (b.p. 126°).

The reactions are followed by the usual argentimetric procedure (Volhard's method).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Second order rate constants for the reactions of methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol and *n*-butanol with HBr in 100% propionic acid, 100% acetic acid, 80 : 20% v/v acetic acid and monochloroacetic acid and 80 : 20% v/v acetic acid and carbon tetrachloride.

Reactions are all second order reactions as plots of $\log a-x/b-x$ or $1/a-x$ Vs time are all linear (Table 1).

As the rate constants reveal, there is a decrease in kinetic rate with the increase of chain length.

TABLE 1

Second order rate constants ($10^3 k$ l. mole⁻¹ min⁻¹) and ρ values for reactions between monohydric alcohols and HBr at 80°

Monohydric alcohols	Acetic acid 100%	Acetic acid-monochloro acetic acid (80 : 20% v/v)	Acetic acid-carbon tetrachloride (80 : 20% v/v)	Propionic acid 100%
Methanol	0.94	1.93	2.00	3.74
Ethanol	0.37	1.65	2.00	1.35
<i>n</i> -Propanol	0.34	1.56	—	1.14
<i>n</i> -Butanol	0.25	1.10	1.02	0.84
ρ	+4.30	+2.00	+2.33	+4.60

$\rho\sigma$ plot : Plots of $\log k$ Vs σ for simple aliphatic primary alcohols gave ρ values +4.3, +2.0, +2.33 and +4.6 for the various solvent systems studied respectively. The sign of the value is not at variance with the postulate that electron releasing groups are favouring reaction. The reversal of sign might be due to steric effect overweighing the polar effect of the alkyl groups. One can also say that due to hyper conjugation effect becoming important due to conjugate acid formation, the effect of the alkyl group will be methyl > ethyl > *n*-propyl > *n*-butyl, and this is reflected in the rate differences.

Solvent effect : This is clear that addition of a hydrocarbon component like carbon tetrachloride accelerates the reaction. With monochloro acetic acid the reaction rates are higher than pure acetic acid as the increase in acidity influences the rate even though there is a slight increase in the dielectric constant due to monochloro acetic acid. The fastness of propionic acid is similar to whatever has been observed by us earlier.

Reaction of diols with HBr : Ethylene glycol, propylene glycol and 1 : 3 butane diol have been subjected to reaction with HBr in acetic acid-benzene mixture, acetic acid and acetic acid-acetonitrile mixture at 40°, 50° and 60°.

Second order rate constants ($10 k$ l. mole⁻¹ min⁻¹) for reactions between diols and HBr are given below (Tables 2-4).

TABLE 2

Solvent : acetic acid 100%

Diols	40°	50°	60°
Ethylene glycol	3.35	10.00	20.00
Propylene glycol	2.12	6.87	13.55
1 : 3 Butane diol	0.15	0.40	—

TABLE 3

Solvent : Acetic acid—acetonitrile (80 : 20% v/v)

Diols	40°	50°	60°
Ethylene glycol	2.33	8.12	10.00
Propylene glycol	1.71	5.18	7.26
1 : 3 Butane diol	0.13	0.35	0.80

TABLE 4

Solvent : Acetic acid—benzene (80 : 20% v/v)

Diols	40°	50°	60°
Ethyleneglycol	3.84	12.98	21.82
Propylene glycol	3.08	8.59	14.29
1 : 3 Butane diol	0.25	0.48	1.33

Effect of structure : The kinetic rate denotes that the reactivity is ethylene glycol > propylene glycol > 1 : 3 butane diol as found earlier (*loc. cit.*). The first displacement rates are computed as the second displacements are too slow to measure. The larger the separation of hydroxyls the lower the kinetic rate indicating that neighbouring hydroxyls were participating in anchimeric assistance.

Effect of amines : The effect of amines like *n*-butyl amine and benzyl amine on the reaction of ethylene glycol with HBr in glacial acetic acid is studied. It was found that the reaction virtually stopped. The reason might be the formation of the onium salts. $\text{RNH}_2 + \text{HBr} \rightarrow \text{RNH}_3^+ + \text{Br}^-$. The proton availability for conjugate acid formation is nil and hence no substitution occurs. As postulated earlier conjugate acid formation is the first feature of the reaction. When it is not possible, there is certainly no substitution.

Effect of potassium acetate : The reaction of ethylene glycol with HBr in glacial acetic acid is also studied. The reaction stopped virtually and there is no substitution as found by the constancy of HBr concentration due to the reaction $\text{CH}_3\text{COOK} + \text{HBr} \rightarrow \text{KBr} + \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$. The proton availability for conjugate acid formation and the hydroxylic oxygen becomes always nil and the reaction stops.

Thermodynamic parameters : For the alcohol-HBr reactions this is the first systematic report of thermodynamic parameters. All the thermodynamic parameters are given below for the various solvent mixtures.

Thermodynamic parameters for reaction between diols and HBr (Table 5-7).

TABLE 5

Solvent : Acetic acid—benzene (80 : 20% v/v)

Diols	E K.cals.	ΔH K.cals.	Log_{10}PZ	ΔS cal/mole	$\text{C} + \beta\Delta\text{S}$
Ethylene glycol	18.31	17.69	10.59	-10.21	17.58
Propylene glycol	18.76	18.61	10.81	- 9.17	18.83
1 : 3 Butane diol	20.60	19.98	11.00	- 8.31	19.86

TABLE 6

Solvent : Acetic acid 100%

Diols	E K.cals.	ΔH K.cals.	$\text{Log}_{10}PZ$	ΔS cal/mole	$C+\beta\Delta S$
Ethylene glycol	15.10	14.48	8.29	-20.72	14.17
Propylene glycol	15.56	14.94	8.41	-18.58	15.88
1 : 3 Butane diol	18.31	17.69	9.08	-17.10	17.07

TABLE 7

Solvent : Acetic acid—acetonitrile (80 : 20% v/v)

Diols	E K.cals.	ΔH K.cals.	$\text{Log}_{10}PZ$	ΔS cal/mole	$C+\beta\Delta S$
Ethylene glycol	16.03	15.41	8.78	-18.47	15.05
Propylene glycol	16.47	15.75	8.95	-17.71	16.26
1 : 3 Butane diol	18.31	17.69	9.12	-16.92	17.55

Plot of $\log_{10} k$ Vs $1/T$ were linear. Plots of $\log_{10} PZ$ against $1/\sqrt{E}$ give straight line as it should be on the basis of thermodynamic considerations if both the Arrhenius parameters are the controlling factors of the kinetic rates⁵.

The small frequency factor would mean that the standard entropy activation has relatively a large negative value or that the transmission coefficient is small, the latter is probably true in a number of instances. Small frequency factors are of course known for bimolecular processes involving fairly complex molecules having a large number of degree of freedom.

There is a linear relationship between enthalpy and entropy of activations. Leffler and Grunwald⁶ have pointed out that many reactions show an iso-kinetic relationship of the form $\Delta H = C + \beta\Delta S$. The linearity can also be seen by comparing the values of ΔH and $C + \beta\Delta S$. This indicates that the rate is much lower than the calculated one from collision theory, P values being lower than unity.

Dependence on dielectric constant : Plots of $\log_{10} k$ and $1/D$ are linear for acetic acid ($D = 6.15$), acetic acid—benzene ($D = 5.374$) and acetic acid—acetonitrile ($D = 12.42$) mixtures indicating that these reactions can be treated as positive ion dipolar reactions. The reactions are accelerated with a decreasing dielectric constant. The reaction as mentioned earlier is a bimolecular displacement of which the initial step is the formation of a conjugate acid at the hydroxylic oxygen. This means that one can treat this as a positive ion dipolar reaction. An analogy is found in the acid catalysed hydrolytic reactions of esters where Amis⁷ has treated the reactions as positive ion dipolar reactions.

Mechanism : (1) *Monohydric alcohols* : The reaction consists of an attack on the etheral oxygen followed by Br⁻ attack on the nucleophilic carbon. It could occur depending on substrate by both unimolecular and bimolecular mechanism.

But kinetics cannot unequivocally establish which mechanism is operating. Bond fission seems much more significant than bond formation as electron releasing groups are favouring reaction.

As the medium is of low dielectric constant, possibly a bimolecular reaction may not be pure SN² process but SN² ion pair mechanism may be operating.

(2) *Dihydric alcohols* : It has been postulated earlier that these reactions proceed as follows :

OH participation leading to the epoxide seems to be reasonable. The possibility of the formation of an epoxide exists for all the diols but the possibility of opening of the ring giving rise to the products is likely to be very high in the case of ethylene glycol. The larger the ring the more the stability and hence the reaction rate is slower. Progressively there is a decrease in the rate of first displacement as the position of hydroxyls is varied.

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